

Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem
Ocean Observations

Co-Creating a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science: Fostering Collaboration for a Sustainable Future

Focus Group at the 7th International Marine Conservation Congress
(IMCC7)

13 October 2024, Cape Town, South Africa

REPORT

Authors	Artur Palacz, Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Dominik Krzywiński
Citation	Palacz AP, Nordlund LM, Krzywiński D (2025). Report on the Focus Group on Co-Creating a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science: Fostering Collaboration for a Sustainable Future at the 7 th International Marine Conservation Congress, 13 October 2024, Cape Town, South Africa. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15656907

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement number 101136748. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. Introduction

The Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science is a flagship product being developed by the EU Horizon BioEcoOcean project to help advance the coordination and communication around marine life observations. The Blueprint, as it is henceforth referred to in this document, is being designed as a communications support tool, co-created with a broad group of actors holding stakes in the value of ocean observing from local to global scales. The co-creative process of the Blueprint development, and sub-sequent testing through a variety of case studies, takes place through many in-person as well as online workshops, surveys and other interactions with the marine science community at large. For more information on the planned approach to the Blueprint development please see the project website at: <https://bioecocean.org/actions/blueprint-living-lab/>

Based on the first series of workshops internal to the BioEcoOcean consortium, devoted to the conceptual design and early testing of the Blueprint, project members Lina Mtwana Nordlund (Uppsala University) and Artur Palacz (Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences) conducted the first co-creative workshop with stakeholders external to the project consortium. Held on 13 October 2024, the Focus Group session on “Co-Creating a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science: Fostering Collaboration for a Sustainable Future”, was a full-day event organized as a side event to the [7th International Marine Conservation Congress \(IMCC7\)](#) which took place in Cape Town, South Africa, on 13-17 October 2024.

The choice of IMCC7 as the venue for the first external Blueprint co-design workshop was deliberate as it ensured on site access to stakeholders from both inside and outside of academia, potentially providing a perspective from the global coastal ocean to ensure the broad applicability/adequacy of the Blueprint.

2. Focus Group proceedings

The Focus Group was attended by fourteen delegates in marine conservation from across Africa, Asia, North America and Europe who shared their unique perspectives on how to maximize the value of our ocean observations, and this way contributed substantially to the co-creation of the Blueprint at the critical early stage of its conceptual development. Collectively, the delegates provided the expected broad range of expertise and interest relevant to marine life observations and the various elements of the ocean observing value chain. As indicated by Figure 1, there was a uniform distribution of engagement across all the Biology and Ecosystems (BioEco) Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), including the multidisciplinary Ocean Colour, Ocean Sound and Marine Plastics Debris EOVs. Considering the focus of IMCC on conservation, it was not surprising that half of the participants worked with either fish, corals or benthic invertebrates. Climate change was listed as the key concern in terms of threats to marine life, followed by fishing and coastal development (Figure 1).

Unlike in the BioEcoOcean consortium where many partners work with exclusively either with data collection, analysis or modelling, the IMCC7 workshop participants identified primarily with professional activities related to application in society, planning, review, and evaluation (all together over 53%; Figure 2). Their input into the conceptual design of the Blueprint was therefore invaluable, and highly complementary to the input received through the BioEcoOcean consortium workshops.

Figure 1. Breakdown of interest and expertise among the delegates among their self-declared (left) expertise and/or interest in marine organisms grouped according to the Biology & Ecosystems EOVs, and (right) concern with most common threats to marine life.

Figure 2. Self-declared professional activity of the workshop participants mapped onto the components of the draft Blueprint.

During a couple of hours of discussions in plenary and breakout groups, we discussed the challenges of working within and across the different elements of the ocean observing value chain. By sharing their unique experiences from various case studies ranging from shark conservation efforts in the Maldives to monitoring Marine Protected Areas in the UK, the workshop participants revealed key obstacles preventing better coordination and communication in the marine conservation community. Below is a brief summary of key points discussed under each of the proposed Blueprint components, which continue to help develop the leading questions of the Blueprint, and where relevant, further refine the structure.

3. Focus Group results and conclusions

The participants agreed that efficient and coordinated marine data management was at the heart of ensuring maximum value of our ocean observations. As is, data management faces several challenges, including the need to comply with diverse data standards for various reporting requirements and the limited technical capacity in regions such as Small Island Developing States. Effective management requires the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data, raising questions about the appropriate level of standardization needed for consistent and usable datasets. A key tension exists between standardizing and harmonizing data collection methods, emphasizing the importance of clarity and coordination. Recognition for data sharing is also critical—co-authorship opportunities should extend to

non-academic contributors. Additionally, the lack of automated systems for harvesting data from multiple repositories hampers efficiency. To address these issues, funding agencies must play a more proactive role in setting and enforcing data management standards and creating interoperability between existing centres.

Successful data management enables delivery of data products which are relevant for multiple yet specific applications. Various types and forms of indicators of change are particularly needed as such products stemming from raw data. Key aspect is the timeliness of data product development, recognizing that today most of the data is being published too late and is thus too old to be useful for scientific assessments upon which policy and science-based decision-making rely. Historical data remains critical also for model development and evaluation. Delegates pointed at the vital need to build data products also on the basis of wealth of data collected by industry - data which today remains largely inaccessible to the science community. Successful use of data and model outputs in policy depends on whether and how we report uncertainty of our projections. The apparent need for establishing better metrics of reporting uncertainty to the end users was mentioned as a challenge, often exacerbated by the fact that end users do not want to recognize uncertainty in the science products.

Among other issues discussed were the need for wider access to remote observing technologies to increase data coverage and resolution; the need for reporting failures as well as successes as an essential basis for proper evaluation of the observing system; more effective integration of indigenous knowledge and community involvement in ocean observations; and environmental stewardship as integral to planning observing campaigns and anticipating potential side effects.

Based on the results of these discussions, the BioEcoOcean Team has developed an improved version of the Blueprint conceptual design (Figure 3) and used the conclusions as well as workshop evaluation feedback to improve the next round of stakeholder workshops aimed to further develop and test the applicability and usefulness of the current Blueprint design.

Figure 3. The second updated version of the spiderwebbed Blueprint. Following an iterative process facilitated by the IMCC7 Focus Group discussions, an additional component - Evaluation - was added to the Blueprint conceptual design.